

Effect of Variation in Processing Conditions on Thermal and Mechanical Properties of Ternary Nylon-6 Blends

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The versatility of Nylon-6 (NY-6) as an engineering plastic is limited due to its poor impact strength, poor processibility and higher moisture pick up. These limitations are overcome to a greater extent by blending it with low density polyethylene (LDPE) and LDPE-g-butyl acrylate (LDPE-g-BuA) an interfacial agent^{1,2}. In our earlier work^{1,2} we have reported the effect of variation in composition of Nylon-6 ternary blends on blend properties. In the present work the effects of processing conditions with respect to variation in temperature in extruder on the final mechanical properties while keeping the compositions of the blends same, are discussed. The blends are also thoroughly studied for their thermal and structural properties.

Results and Discussion

The effect of varying processing conditions on the morphology of the blends was studied through scanning electron microscopy. In the present system variation in processing conditions within the range

studied did not show any change in particle dimension and roughness of the fractured surface. Hence it can be predicted that there is little effect on adhesion of polymeric phases due to variation in processing conditions.

Nylon-6 (NY-6) exists mainly in four major structures: (i) amorphous state, (ii) pseudo-hexagonal (γ) phase, (iii) hexagonal (β) phase and (iv) monoclinic cell (α) phase. From the X-ray scattering curve, it can be inferred that for all the blends, the intensity of the peak $2\theta=11^\circ$ is found to be lower and the peak corresponding to $2\theta=21.1^\circ$ ($d=4.22 \text{ \AA}$) is observed to split into two peaks. This indicates that in all the blends with addition of LDPE/LDPE-g-BuA γ -form transforms to α -form. However, the variation in processing conditions is not found to make any significant difference in structural transformation.

It can be observed from thermograms that within the range studied the variation in processing conditions and reprocessing of the blends do not influence

TABLE 1—FORMULATIONS OF THE VARIOUS NY-6/LDPE/LDPE-g-BuA BLENDS PREPARED BY VARYING PROCESSING CONDITIONS

Blend code	NY-6 % (w/w)	LDPE % (w/w)	Interfacial agent LDPE-g-BuA (D.G. = 6.7%) % w/w	Mixing temp. (°C)				Rotor speed r p.m.
				Zone-1	Zone-2	Zone-3	Zone-4	
a ₁	85.0	14.6	2.4	220	260	265	260	30
a ₁₁	83.0	14.6	2.4	220	260	265	260	30
a ₂	83.0	14.6	2.4	220	260	265	255	30
a ₃	83.0	14.6	2.4	220	260	265	250	30
a ₃₃	83.0	14.6	2.4	220	260	265	250	30
a ₄	83.0	14.6	2.4	220	250	260	250	30

TABLE 2—THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND PERCENTAGE WATER ABSORPTION OF VARIOUS BLENDS

Blend code	Tensile strength kg cm ⁻²	Flexural strength kg cm ⁻²	Elongation at break %	Izod impact strength kg-cm/cm of notch	Water absorption %	Rockwell hardness RHR	Heat distortion temp. °C	Vicat softening temp. °C
a ₁	548	651	55	4.73	2.35	111.0	51.5	211.5
a ₂	536	671	64	4.82	2.26	111.5	51.0	211.0
a ₃	656	696	54	4.54	1.90	112.0	51.0	211.0
a ₄	468	638	99	5.18	2.44	111.0	51.0	211.5
a ₁₁ *	547	658	59	4.63	2.40	—	—	—
a ₃₃ *	650	682	54	4.60	2.00	—	—	—

*Double extruded blend.

the melting and crystallisation temperatures of NY-6 and LDPE present in the blends. However, the a₁, a₂ and a₃ blends were found to have higher crystallinity index (≈30) than that of a₄ blend (≈20). Reprocessing of the blend was not found to affect the crystallinity index value.

In Table 2 the tensile strength, flexural strength, percentage elongation at break and Izod impact strength of the various blends prepared at different processing conditions are given. It can be inferred that the a₁, a₂ and a₃ blends have higher tensile and flexural strength than that of a₄ blend. As the morphology and structural properties of all the blends are same, this relatively higher value of the tensile and flexural strength of blends can probably be attributed to their higher crystallinity value. Again the marginally improved tensile and flexural strength of a₃ blend than that of a₁ and a₂ blends is also probably due to relatively higher crystallinity of the blends. Probably due to the same factor the elongation at break value and impact strength of a₁, a₂ and a₃ blends are also observed to be reduced. Further, the lower impact strength of a₁ than that of a₃ may be due to its lower percentage of crystallinity and lower crystallite size. It can be inferred that the mechanical properties are not influenced by extrusion of the blend.

The water absorption extent value of the blends are given in Table 2. As the a₁, a₂ and a₃ blends have relatively higher crystallinity, they show slightly lower water absorption than the a₄ blend. Rockwell hardness, Vicat softening temperature and heat distortion temperature of the blends are independent of the processing conditions.

Experimental

The Nylon-6 with number average molecular weight (M_n) of 25000, melt flow index 0.5 g/10 min and LDPE with viscosity average molecular weight (M_v) of 52000 and melt flow index 0.2 g/10 min were supplied by Gujarat State Fertilizer Co. Ltd., and Indian Petrochemicals Corporation Ltd., respectively. The synthesis of LDPE-g-BuA is reported earlier³.

A Haake 40 rheometer coupled with single screw extruder was used for the preparation of the blends. The various formulations of the blends prepared by varying the extruder temperature are reported in Table 1. The representative blends a₁₁ and a₃₃ have been processed twice in extruder to check the morphological stability during processing. The compounded pellets were injection-molded to obtain the test specimens.

Tensile properties, izod impact strength and flexural strength measurements were carried out according to ASTM D 638, D 256 and D 790 respectively. Percentage water absorption of the conditioned samples (5.4 × 1.8 × 0.3 cm) was measured by difference in the weight after keeping the sample in boiling water for 2 h (Table 2). Rockwell hardness (RHR), Vicat softening temperature (VST) and heat distortion temperature were measured according to ASTM D 785, ASTM D 1525 and ASTM D 648 respectively. The thermal properties were studied using a DuPont 900 analyser.

Scanning electron micrograph and X-ray data were taken as reported earlier¹.

NOTES

References

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